

Characterisation of ceramic fibre preforms

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Abstract

The preforms used in the liquid metal infiltration for fabricating metal matrix composites (MMC) differ in part considerably concerning their quality and infiltration behaviour. As a result, there occurs an enduring influence on the desired characteristics of a MMC.

In the present paper, we present the thermogravimetric analysis that enables to perform a qualitative characterisation of these preforms by means of random sample measurements. Thus, statements about the inner structure, about possible material defects and about processing parameters can be issued already before quality control. Examples of measurements on Saffil short staple preforms, C-continuous filament preforms and hybrid short staple preforms are given in order to explain this analysis method.

Keywords: preform, characterisation, metal matrix composites, MMC, thermogravimetric analysis

1. Introduction

Whereas fibre reinforced plastics as modern engineering materials have already found a wide field of applications, fibre reinforced metals still lie midway between development and industrial application. Much interest is spent on the improvement in mechanical properties of light metals as titanium, aluminum or magnesium by the carefully directed incorporation of reinforcements such as ceramic fibres. Fibre reinforced light metals are fabricated mostly by liquid metal infiltration methods as for example the squeeze-casting process or the infiltration under constant applied pressure. During the fabrication, an homogeneous distribution of the fibres in the metal matrix is of an overall importance and has to be assured.

Here, the application of preforms has proved its performance. The preforms generally consist of a fixed proportion of fibres that can be oriented in different manners according to the applied fabrication process. The type of fibre used exerts no influence on the fabrication process. Only the criteria of chemical and mechanical compatibility with the later used matrix

metal determine which type of fibre to use.

2. Fabrication of preforms /1/

2.1 Short staple preforms

The different steps of the fabrication of preforms are illustrated in Fig. 1. After having dissolved the fibre agglomerations in water, shots $>100\mu\text{m}$ (non fiberised material) are separated from the pure fibre material in a washing process. In a next step, an inorganic binder (amorphous SiO_2 or Al_2O_3) is added providing a sufficient burning resistance necessary for the preform. Then, starch is added as a flocculent in order to start the so-called flocking process (see Fig. 2). By this process the variation of the similar potentials of the fibre and the inorganic binder (similar potentials cause repelling forces) is introduced making precipitate the binder on the fibre. This happens primarily in the area of the crossing points of the fibres, leading to a good stabilization of the fibres with a relatively low content of binder. As a rule, a high content of binder has to be avoided for the following reasons:

Fig.1: Fabrication process of short staple preforms

Fig.2: Illustration of the flocking process /1/

- it can cause the formation of "sails" affecting the infiltration with the liquid metal (Fig. 3).
- it can cause the coating of the fibre, having a great impact on the formation of boundaries (Fig. 3).
- after burning, it can lead to the formation of bulks of residues from the organic binder, reducing considerably the infiltration facility (Fig. 4).

Fig.3: formation of "sails" and coating of fibres in preforms

Fig. 4: Residues of binder after sintering

The fibres are formed and oriented in a vacuum process: first, the water is extracted from the fiberised material lying in a mould. In the following squeezing process, the fibre density is adjusted with the applied pressure. The remaining water is extracted in a drying process. By adding organic starch, the green strength of the preform is improved significantly. This is necessary, as the inorganic binder is not curing before being burnt. While the starch is burning out, the amorphous inorganic binder is becoming crystalline.

2.2 Continuous filament preforms

The fabrication of continuous filament preforms and short staple preforms differ concerning the dispersement of fibres impossible in the case of continuous filament preforms. As a consequence, the flocking process described in 2.1 above cannot take place. The binder is added progressively by passing the filament through a bath of binder. As continuous filaments do not cross each other, the fibres are fixed by means of a bridge formed between them due to the transformation into a precisely defined jelly-like state of the binder during the drying process (Fig. 5: a,b) deposition of the binder; c) formation of "sails"). A very precise process control is crucial in order to avoid a formation of "sails" impeding the infiltration.

3. Characterisation of ceramic fibre preforms

The characterisation of preforms is necessary for the liquid metal fabrication process of MMCs as well as for the later quality control of the fabricated composites. It includes the following aspects:

- content of fibres
- mechanical strengths
- fibre distribution
- temperature limits (especially for preforms containing carbon)
- optimum burning-out times and temperatures for the burning-out process
- contents of binders and binder distribution
- proportion of each reinforcing component in the case of hybrid preforms
- recognition of defaults in preforms as for example agglomerations, delaminations, shots.

Fig.5: Deposition of binder on continuous filament fibres /1/

Whereas the first and the second point enumerated above can be determined quite easily by already known processes as density determination or compression/bending tests, the remaining points can be treated only with a partly high experimental and analytical operational extent. The process presented in this paper permits to determine in part these characteristics by a thermogravimetric analysis.

4. Description of the measurement process

The thermogravimetric analysis method permits to plot directly the weight variation of a preform sample with time and temperature. Two different methods have to be distinguished:

- registration of the burning-out behaviour during dynamic heating
- registration of the burning-out behaviour during isothermal annealing of the sample.

Both methods will be presented by means of investigation results. The following processing parameters have been selected for the measurements:

atmosphere: air	heating	
	dynamic	isothermal
initial temperature (°C)	30	30
heating rate (K/min)	10	20
final temperature (°C)	1030	450/500
holding time (min)	30	70

In order to get a maximum amount of information, it is recommended to use unburned preforms.

5. Investigation results

5.1 Burning-out behaviour of Saffil short staple preforms (Supplier: Didier Corp., Germany)

The used preform material contains 20% of RF-Saffil fibre, an Al_2O_3 short staple fibre of the ICI-Company. SiO_2 is used as inorganic binder.

Fig. 6 illustrates the typical burning-out curve for this material when subjected to dynamic heating.

Fig.6: Burning-out behaviour of a Saffil preform

The weight variation with temperature can be divided into four regions:

- A: In this region, the reduction in weight is due to the evaporation of the water contained in the preform. When the preforms are stocked under normal conditions, it can be reckoned with a content of water of 0.5 - 0.7 wt%, because the preforms are hygroscopic to a slight degree.
- B: The preform is dry, the organic binder is stable.
- C: An important loss of weight occurs due to the decomposition of the organic binder. In the case of the Didier preform that has been our object of investigation, the loss of weight can be settled in the range of 4.5 - 5.0 wt%. The used type of binder determines mainly the evolution of the curve that can be divided under certain circumstances, as it is the case here, into two sections C1 and C2 when two different

organic binders have been used. C1 and C2 stand for the different decomposition behaviour of the starch products.

- D: After the decomposition of the organic binder, the inorganic binder is converted from its amorphous to its crystalline state. This reaction does not affect the weight of the sample. A slight loss of weight is due to the not easily exchange of the gases formed during the burning of the organic binder present in the preform with the surrounding atmosphere.

Based on the explications above we can issue the following statements:

- * The investigated preforms are containing 0.5 - 0.7 wt% of water.
- * The decomposition of the inorganic binder begins at a temperature of about 250°C.
- * At temperatures ranging from 550°C to 600°C, this burning-out process is terminated, i.e., after an interval of about 30 min. the mayor part of the starch has been removed from the preform.
- * The absolute content of organic binder can be settled in the range of 4.5 - 5.0 wt%.

By performing random sample measurements further information about the inner structure of the preform is obtained.

Comparing the absolute values of loss of weight of random samples during the burning-out process, information about the binder distribution is obtained. The distribution should be as regular as possible in order to avoid inhomogeneities.

As we have seen above in the so-called flocking-process, starch is added in order to create a potential difference between reinforcing component and inorganic binder. By this means, the deposition of the starch/inorganic binder mixture on the fibre is reached mainly at the crossing points of the latter . By comparing different measurements, information is obtained about the distribution of the inorganic binder and thus about the fibre distribution.

If the distribution is regular, an identical burning-out behaviour will result, the curves will be identical and cover each other (see Fig. 6, measurement 1 and 2). The more the curves and the absolute values differ from each other, the less regular is the inner structure of the preform (see Fig. 6, measurement 3). In addition, by performing such comparative random sample measurements, defaults in preforms as for example delaminations are becoming observable.

By defining a certain spread of losses of weight during the burning-out process, it is possible to distinguish the preforms referring to their quality.

5.2 Burning-out behaviour of C-continuous filament preforms (Supplier: Didier Corp., Germany)

For guaranteeing a good quality of the preforms, they have to be preheated before infiltration with liquid metal. This is especially problematic in the case of carbon fibre preforms because on the one hand, the organic binder has to be burned out, but on the other, the carbon fibre must not be damaged by oxidation during the preheating process. Burning-out tests with C-continuous filament preforms have been performed (type of fibre: Toray T 700 S) for this purpose. Fig. 7 shows two isothermal burning-out curves at different annealing temperatures. In this diagram, two regions have to be distinguished:

- A: Here, the preform is heated with a heating rate of 20 K/min. During this time, the

water and the organic binder, the latter occupying about 2.5 - 3.5 wt% are removed.

- B: The isothermal temperature has been reached. The slight bending of the continuously plotted curve points to a loss of not easily volatilized particles of the organic binder. According to this, after an annealing time of 70 min. it still has to be reckoned with little binder residues. However, the fibre has not oxidized. The discontinuously plotted curve shows a progressive loss of weight. This makes conclude to an important oxidation of the carbon fibre.

Fig.7: Burning-out behaviour of a C-continuous filament preform

The present investigation illustrates corresponding to the iso-thermal burning-out curves (for the Toray T 700 S fibre) a critical temperature limit at 450 °C in air. Above this temperature, the oxidation of the carbon fibre can no more be excluded.

Single reinforcing proportions for hybrid preforms can be determined as well considering the burning- out curves, on condition that one of the components consists of carbon.

Fig. 8 gives an example for this case. The material that was to investigate consisted of an Al₂O₃/C-short staple fibre mixture. The continuous burning-out curve shows a stabilisation of the loss of weight at 65 wt%. This means that the preform consists of 35 wt% carbon fibres and 65 wt% of Al₂O₃ fibres respectively.

6. Summary

The thermogravimetric analysing process presented in this paper allows to obtain important information for the characterisation of preforms in view of the liquid metal fabrication process of metal matrix composites by means of random samples. Two analysing methods have to be distinguished: the dynamic and the isothermal heating. Knowledge of the content of binder and of the proportions of the components is gained from the evolution and the

absolute values of the plotted burning-out curves. Furthermore, information about the macroscopic structure of the preform is obtained by comparing various random sample

Fig.8: Burning-out behaviour of an Al_2O_3 -/C-short staple preform

measurements under these aspects. Likewise, due to this method, optimum time/temperature intervals for the preheating process can be worked out in order to avoid the deterioration of the preform as well as to optimize the preheating process as such from the economic point of view.

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